

to Mr. N. C. Vardhacharyulu, Principal, Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya, Nanded, for facilities. Thanks are also due to Dr. B. M. Bhawal and B. B. Idge, N.C.L., Pune, for ir spectra.

References

1. T. FAQUDA, *Ardu. Exptl. Pathol. Pharmacol.*, 1932, 164, 585; D. DONNELLY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 872; K. P. JADHAV and D. B. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1963, 22, 150; G. JONGEBREGER, *Arch. Int. Pharmacodynamia*, 1952, 90, 384; K. A. THAKAR, D. D. GOSWAMI and D. G. PACHPOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 420; V. P. KHILYA, V. SZABO, L. G. GRISHKO and M. G. SPASENOV, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 83, 20615; V. P. KHILYA, L. G. GRISHKO, A. V. TUROV and M. G. SPASENOV, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, 96, 351501.
2. V. M. GURAV and U. K. JAGWANI, *Marathwada Univ. J. of Sci.*, 1975, 14, 5.
3. R. S. RASSMUSSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1068.
4. H. L. HERBERT and P. F. KURTH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 75, 1623.

Synthesis and Spectroscopic Studies of some 2-Amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridines

S. S. VERMA, POONAM TANEJA, LALIT PRAKASH* and

R. L. MITAL

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 10 June 1987, accepted 10 August 1988

CYANOPYRIDINES exhibit various biological activities^{1,2}. During the last few years only a few cyanopyridine derivatives have been synthesised by Michael reaction³ and by other methods⁴. In view of the biological activity of cyanopyridines, we

have synthesised a number of new 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridines, characterised by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral studies.

Experimental

The chalcones have been synthesised according to the reported method⁴. Melting points are uncorrected.

2-Amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridines: A mixture of chalcone (1 mol), dicyanomethane (1 mol) and ammonium acetate (8 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (150 ml) for 8-10 h on a water-bath. The cooled contents were then poured in ice with constant stirring to obtain a solid yellow mass, washed with water and rectified spirit, and the residue was crystallised by using a mixture of DMF and ethanol (Table 1).

Carbon and hydrogen were analysed by a Coleman 5602 analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃; TMS as internal standard) on a Perkin-Elmer RB-12 spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

The condensation of acetophenones (1 mol) with benzaldehydes (1 mol) in presence of sodium hydroxide and ethanol yielded chalcones (1). The chalcones and dicyanomethane reacted in 1:1 molar ratio in presence of ammonium acetate to give 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridines (2) through Michael reaction with the elimination of water (1 mol each) and hydrogen (Scheme 1). All the cyanopyridines (2) are yellow coloured high melting solids, and soluble in CHCl₃, DMSO and TFA. 2 showed three ir bands at 3 140-3 480 cm⁻¹ (NH₂) and a strong band at 2 220 cm⁻¹ (C≡N); nmr spectra showed the resonances of aromatic ≡CH

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE CYANOPYRIDINES (2)

Sl. no.	R	R ¹	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)	
						C	H
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂	176	88	80.10 (79.70)	5.10 (4.80)
2.	C ₆ H ₅	p-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₂	160	94	80.20 (80.00)	5.27 (5.26)
3.	C ₆ H ₅	p-OOC ₆ H ₅	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ O	170	36	75.55 (75.75)	4.70 (4.98)
4.	C ₆ H ₅	p-Br.C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ BrN ₂	187	28	61.92 (61.71)	3.70 (3.48)
5.	C ₆ H ₅	p-Cl.C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClN ₂	212	30	71.00 (70.70)	3.78 (3.98)
6.	C ₆ H ₅	p-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	203-05	28	68.85 (68.85)	3.50 (3.80)
7.	p-Cl.C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClN ₂	170-72	38	70.30 (70.70)	3.64 (3.98)
8.	p-Cl.C ₆ H ₅	p-Cl.C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂	200	30	63.88 (63.58)	3.54 (3.24)
9.	p-Cl.C ₆ H ₅	p-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClO ₂ N ₂	230-82	50	61.90 (61.68)	3.31 (3.14)

TABLE 2—IR AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE CYANOPYRIDINES (2)

Sl. no.*	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)		δ (CDCl ₃)					
	NH ₂	C≡N (conj)	OH ₂	OCH ₃	≡OH	NH ₂	ArH (R ¹)	ArH (R)
1.	3 440, 3 300, 3 160	2 220s	—	—	7.15(s)	7.25–7.55(bs)	7.72(s)	7.0(s)
2.	3 445, 3 315, 3 170	2 220s	2.48s	—	7.9(s)	7.5–7.7(bs)	7.25(s)	7.8–8.2(d)
3.	3 450, 3 340, 3 140	2 220s	—	3.85s	7.18(s)	7.5–7.7(bs)	6.9–7.1(d)	7.9–8.1(d)
4.	3 470, 3 370, 3 140	2 220s	—	—	7.98(s)	7.5–7.8(bs)	7.28(s)	7.9–8.2(d)
5.	3 480, 3 375, 3 155	2 220s	—	—	7.9(s)	7.5–7.7(bs)	7.2(s)	7.75–8.2(d)
6.	3 440, 3 320, 3 160	2 220s	—	—	7.2(s)	7.5–7.65(bs)	6.8–7.1(d)	7.82–8.3(d)
7.	3 465, 3 365, 3 155	2 220s	—	—	7.82(s)	7.5–7.7(bs)	7.25(s)	7.75–8.3(d)
8.	3 450, 3 355, 3 145	2 220s	—	—	7.84(s)	7.5–7.82(bs)	7.0–7.2(s)	7.85–8.25(d)
9.	3 470, 3 365, 3 140	2 220s	—	—	7.84(s)	7.5–7.8(bs)	7.25(s)	7.85–8.2(d)

*Compd. refers as in Table 1.

Scheme 1

proton (pyridine nucleus) at δ 7.15–7.38, NH₂ protons as a broad singlet at δ 7.25–7.82, aromatic protons-(R¹) at δ 6.8–7.28, aromatic protons-(R) at δ 7.0–8.3, CH₂ protons as a sharp singlet at δ 2.48 and OCH₃ protons as a sharp singlet at δ 3.85 ppm. The ir and nmr spectral data of the cyanopyridines are recorded in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from U.G.C., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- V. SCOTT and E. JOSEPH, Jap. Pat. 7 998 338/1979 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **92**, 82428); V. SCOTT and E. JOSEPH, Ger. Pat. 2 803 592/1979 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **92**, 47916); J. J. BALDWIN, E. L. ENGELHARDT, R. HIRSCHMANN, G. S. PONTICELLO, J. G. ATKINSON, B. K. WASSON, C. S. SWEET and A. SCRIBINE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1980, **23**, 65; C. S. SWEET, A. SCRIBINE, D. WRITZ, C. T. LUDDEN, D. H. MINSKER and C. A. STONE, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1979, **211**, 200; A. SCRIBINE, C. T. LUDDEN, G. MORGAN and J. J. BALDWIN, *Experientia*, 1979, **35**, 1634; C. M. CARSON, R. J. EHR and R. B. ROGERS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **92**, 6597.
- N. LATIF, N. MISHRIKY and N. S. GIRGIS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 147; N. MISHRIKY, N. S. GIRGIS, S. ARNOS and G. A. M. NAWWAR, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1980, **23**, 433; H. H. MOUSSA and L. M. CHABAKA, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1983, **26**, 267; D. E. MCCLURE, J. J. BALDWIN, W. C. RANDALL, T. F. LYON, K. MENSLER, G. F. LUNDELL, A. W. RAAB, D. GROSS and E. A. RISLEY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1983, **26**, 649; H. TAKAHATA, T. NAKAJIMA and T. YAMAZAKI, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1984, **32**, 1658.
- A. SAKURAI and H. MIDORIKAWA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1968, **41**, 430.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th. ed., Longman, London, 1975.

Antimicrobial Study of some Indole Derivatives

K. N. BHATT, (Miss) A. M. DAVE, N. K. UNDAVIA
and

P. B. TRIVEDI*

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University,
Bhavnagar-364 002

Manuscript received 9 December 1987, revised 29 July 1988,
accepted 2 August 1988

INDOLE derivatives show marked biological properties¹. Hydrazine derivatives² are potent inhibitors of monoamineoxidase enzyme, showing appreciable anticonvulsant activity. Reports reveal that substituted-malonanilic acid hydrazides are biologically important.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and antimicrobial studies of some indole-3-carboxaldehyde malonanilic acid hydrazones (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1